

Apprenticeship and entrepreneurship development among Igbo Traders in anambra state, Nigeria

¹Mbanefo C. Priscilla & ²Prof. G.U Akam

**Department of Business Administration,
Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University Igbariam, Anambra State, Nigeria**

ABSTRACT

The study examined the apprenticeship and entrepreneurship development among Igbo traders in Anambra state Nigeria, Nigeria. Objectives of the study were to: determine the extent to which start-up capital influences apprenticeship and entrepreneurial development of Igbo businesses in Anambra State, Nigeria; ascertain the extent to which business skills influence apprenticeship and entrepreneurial development amongst Igbo business people in Anambra State, Nigeria. This study adopted a survey design that involves asking questions, collecting, and analyzing data from a supposedly representative members of the population at a single point in time with a view to determine the current situation of that population with respect to one or more variable under investigations. The sources of data are primary and secondary sources. The population of the study consist all the Igboartisan, and manufacturers in the selected commercial cities which amounted to four hundred (400) business people such as: traders, skilled workers, and manufacturers in Anambra State, Nigeria which served as the population and sample size of the study (because of its manageable size). The researcher explored mainly the primary data. The instrument used for the data collection is the questionnaire which was designed and administered to Indigenous traders, skilled workers, and manufacturers of Anambra State, Nigeria extraction. Data collected was analyzed using descriptive statistics (frequencies, percentages, mean, and standard deviation) and the inferential statistics such as t-test statistics and the linear regression model. From the Analysis the study found that start-up capital has significant influence on the survival rate among Igbo traders in Anambra State, Nigeria; business skills have significant influence on the survival rate among Igbo traders in Anambra State, Nigeria. It was recommended among others that; To ensure that start-up capital is dully provided to apprentice, parents and representative of the apprentice should ensure a legally documented agreement between the master and the apprentice. Parents and representatives of the apprentice should advise their ward on the need to be patient and diligent to carefully learn the business skills from the master because this is the basis for apprenticeship.

Keywords: apprenticeship, entrepreneurship development, start-up capital, business skill & Igbo traders

INTRODUCTION

The apprenticeship system came to limelight in Nigeria after the Nigerian-Biafran war. Many parents who were left with nothing after the war were forced to send their children between the ages of 8-20 years to learn business, trade, or vocation. This was how the Igbo survivors rebuilt Onitsha, Nnewi, Aba, and other parts of the country after the war in 1970. In the apprenticeship system for instance, the 'Oga' and 'Nwaboyi' agree for a period ranging from 4-7 years whereby the apprentice is to serve and learn a particular business or a vocation from the 'Oga'. Usually, the mode of settlement is contained in the agreement entered by families of both parties (Onyima, Nzewi & Chiekezi, 2017).

Entrepreneurial development has helped in shaping the economy of most of the advanced and developed nations for over a century now. The phenomenal concept has been a topical issue in both developed and developing economies because of the significant and critical roles entrepreneurship has played in building most of the advanced and emerging economies. It has been asserted that entrepreneurship play critical role by contributing to economic growth, job creation, and national income and hence to national prosperity and competitiveness (Irene, B., Chukwuma-Nwuba, Onoshakpor, & Ndeh, 2024) According to Pinto, Pallikkara, Pinto, and Iqbal (2024) entrepreneurship is the dynamic process of creating incremental wealth. The wealth is created by individuals who assume the major risks in terms of equity, time and career commitment or provide value for some products, but value must somehow be infused by the entrepreneur by receiving and locating the necessary skills and resources. Today, the Igbo man system of apprenticeship has contributed immensely to entrepreneurship development, and this suggests that there are behind the scenes principles that drive the apprenticeship system which has enhanced entrepreneurship development in Nigeria Ifechukwu-Jacobs, (2022).

Unfortunately, this trend is gradually dying out. These days, Anambra State business people and entrepreneurs seem to have resorted to abandonment of apprenticeship scheme; it seems to be affecting the business creation, mentoring and entrepreneurial development in the State. A situation which may be catastrophic, as many youths are without gainful employment in the State. If this ugly development continues, it may pose security and economic threats in the future because of massive youth unemployment, kidnapping, “unknown gunmen” touting. It is against this backdrop that this study tends to explore the principles behind the business construct that has enhanced apprenticeship and entrepreneurship development in Anambra State.

.Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this study is to examine apprenticeship and entrepreneurship development amongst the Igbo business people in Anambra State, Nigeria. The proposed specific objectives are to:

- (1) To determine the extent to which start-up capital influences apprenticeship and entrepreneurial development of Igbo businesses in Anambra State, Nigeria.
- (2) To ascertain the extent to which business skills influence apprenticeship and entrepreneurial development amongst Igbo business people in Anambra State, Nigeria.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Conceptual Review

Concept of Apprenticeship

The term apprenticeship generally, is sometimes used colloquially by scholars from different fields of learning such as doctors, engineers, carpenters, journalists etc. to refer to a model of work-based learning that has enabled them to develop the required levels of experience they need in their career and be acknowledged as members of an occupational society (Fuller & Unwin,2013). Apprenticeship is a workforce strategy that helps people connect to a career pathway for many different occupations. It is an on-the-work learning model, which is combined with relevant classroom instructions. The apprentice progressively acquires new skills and applies these learned skills on the job under the supervision of a mentor. On graduation, the apprentice receives an industry recognized credential (Illinoisworknet Centre system, 2019). It is a veritable tool, and one of the fundamental functional perquisites for employment generation and poverty reduction, with menial investment which tends to give a high result in improving the wellbeing of the individual, and also contributes in reducing the unemployment surge among youths (Fajobi, Olatujoye Amusa, & Adedoyin, 2017). Apprenticeship is a common trend in the world in which unemployed are empowered in the country, the globe changing realities of globalization, competitiveness and knowledge-based economy, strongly underscore the importance of training and skills acquisition among workers (International labour organization, 2012).

Theoretical Framework

This section reviews relevant theories for the study; they include Innovation theory of entrepreneurship, Cognitive Apprenticeship theory, Modeling theory, social learning Theory and Cognitive theory of Development. The first is the Schumpeter's theory of innovation. Joseph Schumpeter (1991) propounded the well-known innovation theory of entrepreneurship. He believed that innovation is the key factor in any entrepreneur's field of specialization. He believed that creativity was necessary if any entrepreneur was to accumulate a lot of profit in a heavily competitive market. He also believed that development as consisting of a process which involved reformation on various equipment of products, outputs, marketing, and industrial organization. He believed that entrepreneurship disturb the stationary circular flow of the economy by introducing an innovation and takes the economy to a new level of development. The activities of the entrepreneur represent a situation of disequilibrium as their activities break the routine circular flow. He noted that innovations of entrepreneurs are responsible for the rapid economic development of any country. He viewed entrepreneurship training as responsible for creative destruction that is, education act as an impetus for creating new ideas, improved techniques, new technologies and new products.

The second is the Cognitive Apprenticeship theory proposed by Brown, Collins & Duguid (1989) the theory emphasis on the importance of the process in which a master of a skill teaches the skill to an apprentice. This theory holds that masters of a skill often fail to consider the implicit processes involved in carrying out complex skills when they are teaching novices. The theory brings these tacit processes into open, where apprentices can observe, enact, and practice them with help from the master. Cognitive theory is a theory that attempt to bring tacit process out in the open. It assumes observation, imitation, and modeling.

The third theory by Albert Baudura (1997) in his theory of Modeling which posits that for modeling to be successful, the learner must be attentive, access and retain the information presented, be motivated to learn and be able to accurately reproduce the desired skill. Also, Baudura espoused that the theory of social learning is a theory of learning process and social behavior can be acquired by observing and imitating others. It states that learning is a cognitive process that takes place in a social context and can occur purely through observations or direct instruction.

Vygotsky's Cognitive Development theory (1934) postulated that social interaction is fundamental to cognitive development. The theory comprises of concept such as culture-specific tools, language and thought interdependence and the zone of proximal Development. The three main concepts related to cognitive development (i) Culture is significant in learning (ii) language is the root of culture and (iii) individuals learn and develop within their role in the community.

Acknowledged, the traditional apprenticeship in which apprentice learns a trade by working under a master (mentor), cognitive apprenticeship allows mentor to model behaviour in a real-world context with cognitive modeling. After listening to the master explain exactly what they are doing and thinking as they model the skill, the apprentice identifies relevant behavior and develops a conceptual model of the processes involved. The apprentice then attempts to imitate those behaviors as the master observing and providing coaching. Coaching aids at most critical level the skill level just beyond the apprentice could accomplish by himself. Vygotsky (1978) referred to this as the Zone of Proximal Development and he believed that fostering development within this zone leads to the most rapid development. The coaching process includes additional modeling as necessary, corrective feedback, and reminders of all intended to bring the apprentice's performance closer to that of the masters. As the apprentice becomes more skilled through the repetition of this process, the feedback and instruction provided by the master fades until the apprentice is ideally performing the skill at a close approximation of the master level. (Johnson, 1992) in Edmondson (2006).

This study is anchored on the three theories: - Cognitive Apprenticeship theory, the theory of Modeling and Vygotsky theory of Cognitive Development. The Cognitive Apprenticeship theory proposed by Brown, Collins & Duguid (1989) the theory emphasis on the importance of the process in which a master (mentor) of a skill teaches the skill to an apprentice. This theory holds that masters of a skill often fail to

consider the implicit processes involved in carrying out complex skills when they are teaching novices. Albert Bandura (1997) proposed theory of Modeling which posits that for modeling to be successful, the learner must be attentive, access and retain the information presented, be motivated to learn and be able to accurately reproduce the desired skill. Vygotsky's Cognitive Development theory (1934) postulated that social interaction is fundamental to cognitive development. The theory comprises of concept such as culture-specific tools, language and thought interdependence and the zone of proximal Development. The three main concepts related to cognitive development (i) Culture is significant in learning (ii) language is the root of culture and (iii) individuals learn and develop within their role in the community.

The implication of these theories to this study is that the apprentice comes to the master (mentor) in a novice state, novice to the hidden talents embedded in him and novice to the skills. It is the master who mentors him and brings out these tacit and talent in him through modeling, mentoring, coaching, and guiding. But the apprentice must come with attentiveness, tolerance, access, and retention of information presented, motivation to learn and be able to accurately reproduce the desired result. In the traditional apprenticeship which is the informal education. The apprentice learns through cognitive apprenticeship which allows the master to model behavior in a real-world context with cognitive modeling. From listening and observation, imitation and practicing the apprentice identifies the relevant positive behavior and tacit which the master should bring to open via the process of observation and providing coaching. But at critical level at the point the skill level is beyond what the apprentice could accomplish by himself, this is the point Vygotsky,1979) referred to as Zone of Proximal Development. At this point, coaching aids. That is point of fostering development within this zone leads to the most rapid development. This is where entrepreneurial pedagogy will be responsible for creative destruction. Entrepreneurial pedagogy is through formal education. It also agrees with the UNDP definition of entrepreneurial development which involves enhancing entrepreneurial skills and knowledge through structural training which includes additional modeling as necessary corrective feedback and reminding in order to bring the apprentice performance closer or better than that of the master(mentor). As the apprentice becomes more skilled through the repetition of this process, feedback and instruction provided by the master fades away, bringing the apprentice to a develop entrepreneur with impetus for creating new ideas, improved techniques, new technologies and new products. Thereby moving our present entrepreneurs from just trading entrepreneur to innovative entrepreneurs.

Empirical Reviews

Santhosha, Vikram and Gil, (2024) investigated how Entrepreneurial development programmes (Edps) offered BY RUDSETIS (rural development and self-employment training institutes) influence apprentice in developing this mindset and motivation. Structured questionnaires were used to collect feedback from 386 unemployed trainees from three different training centres as part of a comprehensive method involving 386 unemployed trainees from three different training centres. The study has used quantitative research techniques such as the chi-square test, Wilcoxon signed rank test, and Kruskal Wallis test to analyse the data. The findings show that Edps have a significant positive impact on most trainees' apprenticeship mindset, motivation, and subsequent follow-up quality. This, in turn, contributes to business success. However, a subset of trainees are unaffected by these programmes. The study raises an alarm for Rudsetis, recommending that they increase their efforts for this specific group. Finally, the paper suggests that Rudseti policymakers rethink and possibly reframe their current strategies. the goal should be to instill an entrepreneurial spirit, boost motivation, and improve the quality of follow-up mechanisms in order to ensure that every trainee, current or potential, benefits optimally.

Ashraf, Rahim, Qureshi and Hanif, (2024) investigated converting apprenticeship into entrepreneurial mindset in graduating university students. It was expected that entrepreneurial mindset and entrepreneurial alertness play a significant role in this process. A questionnaire was developed, and data was collected from students either graduating or in their last year of undergraduate studies. Regression analysis using AMOS was conducted to test the relationships among study variables. Results indicate that entrepreneurial mindset and apprenticeship alertness have mediating roles in the process separately.

Entrepreneurial alertness is the most significant mediator in converting the effect of entrepreneurship education into entrepreneurial intentions. Entrepreneurial mindset also partially mediates the effect of apprenticeship education on entrepreneurial intentions. The findings of this study are essential for educational planners and organizations in the entrepreneurial ecosystem to evaluate the effectiveness of entrepreneurial education in training programs. Future studies may consider replicating this study in different physical and cultural settings.

Egwakhe, et. al. (2024) examined the role of apprenticeship and entrepreneurial mindset as a combined panacea to improve outcomes has not received considerable attention, especially in developing countries like Nigeria, where the Fast Moving Consumer Goods (FMCG) firms have maintained sharp decline in their general performance. Therefore, the need to investigate if the entrepreneurial mindset and entrepreneurial competence combined could affect organizational outcomes is appropriate. The study applied the cross-sectional survey research design in obtaining primary data from 383 top, middle, and low-level management staff of selected FMCG in Lagos State, Nigeria. The stratified random sampling technique was utilized. Also, the reliability and validity tests on the adapted questionnaire were considered credible before applying it to this study. Results from the multiple regression analysis revealed that apprenticeship and entrepreneurial mindset significantly have a combined effect on organizational outcome [Adj.R²= 0.186, F(2, 381) = 44.640, p<0.05]. Management should establish a clear vision and mission that aligns with the entrepreneurial spirit and foster continuous learning culture and improvement to enhance overall organizational outcomes.

Kwapisz, et al. (2024) investigates the link between entrepreneurial Mindset and apprenticeship intentions for among business and engineering students. We also analyze how EM changes over time. Our findings indicate that in both domains, ideation correlated with entrepreneurial mindset and apprenticeship intentions. In both domains, altruism was associated with EI. Empathy and interest were related to EI in engineering students, distinct from their business counterparts, whereas open-mindedness and interest correlated with EI. These differences emphasize the need for distinct educational strategies to prepare both business and engineering students for their entrepreneurial paths.

Ifechukwu-Jacobs, (2022) examined the effect of Igbo trade apprenticeship system on unemployment reduction in Onitsha. The specific objectives were as follows: Ascertain the impact of apprentice skill acquisition on unemployment reduction in Onitsha; Ascertain the impact of apprenticeship training system, on unemployment reduction at Onitsha. The research is anchored under the Skill Acquisition Theory were adopted in this study. Primary sources of data were used and the instrument employed in collecting information from the population was through structured questionnaire. The method of analysis used was percentage table and correlation analysis for testing of the research hypotheses. The population of the study was 3085 boss, who has been in the business for more than 10 years and a sample size of 592 was determined using Gorg & Ball formula. The research adopted sampling techniques were purposive sampling. From the analyses tested, the study found that: Apprentice skill acquisition has significant effect on unemployment reduction at Onitsha

Ntadom, Atueyi & Jacobs (2021) examined the effect of career development on organizational performance, a Study of selected higher institution in Anambra State Nigeria. The study was anchored on Self-concept theory of career development. As a cross-sectional survey the research design were used, a structured questionnaire instrument were developed and used for data collection by the researcher to which reflect such options as strongly agree, agree, undecided, disagree and strongly disagree, which is popularly referred as five (5)points likert scale. It was used to obtain information from the respondents. The population of the study comprised of 57, 710 students selected across the five south east states of Nigeria. A sample size of 399students was drawn from the population, using Taro Yamane formular of which three hundred and forty-seven (347) copies of questionnaires were duly completed and returned; showing 96% response rate. Research hypotheses were tested using ANOVA regression analysis which was carried out with the aid of Statistical package for social science (SPSS) version 23. The study found that career development has significant effect on Organizational Performance. In view of the findings, the study recommended that Training should be done on collaborative decision making and problem solving,

geared towards decentralization, Employees should be trained according to the present content of the environment. The reason is that training implies acquiring knowledge to fill the gap between what is known and what should be known.

METHODOLOGY

This study adopted a survey design that involves asking questions, collecting, and analyzing data from a supposedly representative members of the population at a single point in time with a view to determine the current situation of that population with respect to one or more variable under investigations. The sources of data are primary and secondary sources. The primary data was generated from questionnaire that was distributed while carrying out the research, while the secondary data was sourced from internet, textbooks, journals, and Libraries. The population of the study consist all the Igboartisan, and manufacturers in the selected commercial cities which amounted to four hundred (400) business people such as: traders, skilled workers, and manufacturers in Anambra State, Nigeria which served as the population and sample size of the study (because of its manageable size). The researcher explored mainly the primary data. The primary data was obtained from business people in Anambra State like:traders, skilled workers, and manufacturers of Anambra, States extraction using the Focus Group Discussion (FGD) and a structured questionnaire instrument. Secondary sources of literature for the study will be obtained from existing literature in the field of study which are available to the researchers: they are: journals, internet materials, unpublished write-ups etc. The instrument used for the data collection is the questionnaire which was designed and administered to Indigenous traders, skilled workers, and manufacturers of Anambra State, Nigeria extraction. Data collected was analyzed using descriptive statistics (frequencies, percentages, mean, and standard deviation) and the inferential statistics such as t-test statistics and the linear regression model.

Model Specification

The study was designed to assess the apprenticeship and entrepreneurship development amongst the Igbo business people in Anambra State, Nigeria as the study area.

Thus, the model of this study is stated as follows:

The functional form of the model is

$$ED = f(SC, BS,) \dots\dots\dots(1)$$

The mathematical form of the model is

$$ED = \beta_0 + \beta_1 SC + \beta_2 BS + \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

The econometric form of the model is

$$ED = \beta_0 + \beta_1 SC + \beta_2 BS + \alpha_i \dots\dots\dots (3)$$

Where; ED = Entrepreneurship Development proxied by number of years of existence

SC = Start-up Capital

BS = Business Skills

β_0 = Intercept of the model

$\beta_1 - \beta_5$ = Parameters of the model

α_i = Stochastic error term

DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

This chapter deals with the presentation and analysis of data collected from the field of study. The aim is to present the data in an interpretable form so that the variables of the study can be well understood.

Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Table 1: Distribution of Respondents According to Gender

Variable	Frequency	Percent (%)	Cumulative (%)
Male	348	100	100
Female	-	-	-
Total	348	100	

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 1 shows that all the respondents are males and this represents 100% of the respondents that information data were elicited from.

Table 2: Distribution of Respondents According to Age

Variable	Frequency	Percent (%)	Cumulative (%)
18-32	4	1.1	1.1
31-40	46	13.2	14.3
41-50	152	43.7	58.0
51-60	88	25.3	83.3
61-70	58	16.7	100.0
Total	348	100.0	

Source: Field Survey, 2025

As shown in table 4.3, four respondents, representing 1.1% of the respondents are between the ages of 18-32. forty-six respondents, representing 13.2% of the respondents, are between the ages of 31-40. One hundred and fifty-two respondents, representing 43.7% of the respondents, are between the ages of 41-50. Eighty-eight respondents, account for 25.3% of the respondents, between the ages of 51-60, while fifty-eight respondents account for 16.7% of the respondents, are between the ages of 61-70.

Table 3: Distribution of Respondents According to Educational Qualification

Variable	Frequency	Percent (%)	Cumulative (%)
Primary	11	3.2	3.2
Secondary	289	83.0	86.2
Tertiary	48	13.8	100.0
Total	348	100.0	

Source: Field Survey, 2025

From table 3, all the respondents had formal education. Eleven respondents representing 3.2% of the respondents had primary education. Two hundred and eighty-nine respondents representing 83.0% had secondary education while forty-eight respondents representing 13.8% had tertiary education.

Table 4: Distribution of Respondents According to Years of Business Experience in Private Labels

Variable	Frequency	Percent (%)	Cumulative (%)
1-5	81	23.3	23.3
6-10	185	53.2	76.5
11-15	78	22.4	98.9
15-30	4	1.1	100.0
Total	348	100.0	

Source: Field Survey, 2025

With respect to business experience in private label, table 4.4 reveals that Eighty-one respondents representing 23.3% of the respondents had 1-5years business experience. One hundred and eighty-five respondents representing 53.2% of the respondents had 6-10years business experience. Seventy-eight respondents representing 22.4% of the respondents had 11-15years business experience, while Four respondents representing 1.1% of the respondents had 15-30years business experience.

Table 5: Distribution of Respondents According to Marital Status

Variable	Frequency	Percent (%)	Cumulative (%)
Married	296	85.1	85.1
Single	47	13.5	98.6
Widow/Widower	5	1.4	100.0
Total	348	100.0	

Source: Field Survey, 2025

From table 5, Two hundred and ninety-six respondents representing 85.1% of the respondents are married. Forty-seven respondents representing 13.5% of the respondents are single, while five respondents representing 1.4% of the respondents are widow/widower.

Table 6: Distribution According to Respondents Position

Variable	Frequency	Percent (%)	Cumulative (%)
Owner/CEO	217	62.4	62.4
Apprentice	131	37.6	100.0
Total	348	100.0	

Source: Field Survey, 2025

With respect to respondents' position, two hundred and seventeen respondents representing 62.4% of the respondents are Owner/CEO, while One hundred and thirty-one respondents representing 37.6% of the respondents are apprentice.

Table 7: Effect of start-up capital on the Survival Rate of Igbo business people in Anambra State, Nigeria

Variables	N	Mean	Std Dev	Remark
The apprentice parents cannot provide cash before going to their masters.	348	4.03	1.177	Accepted
The apprentice does not have access to informal credit facilities while on training	348	4.30	0.716	Accepted
The apprentice does not have easy access to formal credit facilities while on training	348	4.13	0.911	Accepted
The number of years served by the apprentices no not increase the amount of the cash infusion.	348	4.51	0.551	Accepted
Some apprentices lack responsiveness to opportunity	348	4.38	0.701	Accepted
Poor cash infusion result to poor survival rate.	348	4.06	0.945	Accepted
Grand Mean		4.24	0.834	Accepted

Source: Field Survey, 2025

All the variables met the theoretical mean threshold of 3.0 which is the established mean cut-off. Thus, the descriptive statistics suggests that start-up capital has influenced the survival rate of Igbo traders in Anambra State, Nigeria with a grand mean of 4.24.

Table 8: Effect of Business Skills on the Survival Rate of Igbo business people in Anambra State, Nigeria

Variables	N	Mean	Std Dev	Remark
Apprentices do daily booking keeping of the business account	348	4.46	0.721	Accepted
Without the master, apprentice can negotiate price of good with the customers	348	3.48	1.382	Accepted
Apprentices maintain the customer service by networking	348	3.65	1.172	Accepted
Apprentices learn the verbal communication skill to communicate and a have ease of customer acquisition.	348	3.74	1.055	Accepted
Apprentices knowledge helps him to gather, interpret and use penitent information about the business environment.	348	3.52	1.066	Accepted
Some apprentices lack the tenacity for competition that improves the survival rate of the business	348	4.25	1.113	Accepted
Grand Mean		3.85	1.085	Accepted

Source: Field Survey, 2025

As shown in table 8, all the variables on effect of business skills on the survival rate of Igbo traders in Anambra State, Nigeria construct met the theoretical mean threshold of 3.0. We, therefore, conclude that business skills have influenced the survival rate of Igbo traders in Anambra State, Nigeria with a grand mean of 3.85.

Regression Analysis Result

Table 9: Regression Result on Apprenticeship and Entrepreneurship Development Among Igbo business people in Southeast Nigeria

Model	B	Std. error	T	Sig.
Constant(C)	0.025	0.006	4.449	0.000
Start-up capital	0.699	0.063	11.018	0.000
Business Skills	0.556	0.092	6.029	0.020
R	0.529			
R²	0.889			
Adj. R²	0.841			
F-statistic	221.401			0.000

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Dependent Variable: Years of Business Experience

To ascertain the effect of apprenticeship on entrepreneurship development among Igbo traders in Anambra state Nigeria, the weighted mean of the two independent variables were regressed on the dependent variable to enable us determine the nature of relationship between the dependent and independent variables, effect of the two independent variables on the dependent variable, the overall fitness of the model using the F-statistics and probability value and the level of significance of the independent variables in influencing the dependent variables using the t-test and probability value. The table above shows the regression result. It also shows the precision of the model which was analyzed using economic a priori criteria and statistical criteria.

Discussion based on economic a priori criteria

Discussion using this criterion enables us to determine the nature of relationship between the dependent and independent variables. In this case, the sign and magnitude of each variable coefficient are evaluated against theoretical or economic a priori criteria/expectations. As showed in the table 9, it is observed that the regression line has a positive intercept as presented by the constant (c) = 0.025. This means that if all the variables are held constant or fixed (zero), the entrepreneurship development among Igbo traders in Anambra state, Nigeria increases by 2.5%. The result also conforms to the a priori expectation. This states that the intercept could be positive or negative, so it conforms to the theoretical expectation (Gujarati, 2008).

Start-up capital has a positive relationship with entrepreneurship development among Igbo traders in Anambra State Nigeria. This implies that the start-up capital and entrepreneurship development among Igbo traders in Anambra State, Nigeria increase in the same direction. That is to say that start-up capital has a direct and positive relationship with entrepreneurship development among Igbo traders in Anambra State, Nigeria. In other words, 1% increase in start-up capital will bring about 69.9% growths in the entrepreneurship development among Igbo traders in Anambra State Nigeria.

This finding is in line with the finding of Onyima, Nzewi and Chiekezie (2017) in effect of apprenticeship and social capital on new business creation process of Igbo ‘Immigrant’ entrepreneurs in Wukari, Taraba State which revealed that social capital is very important and serves as a source of insurance for the business to be established. Also, Ezenwakwelu, Egbosionu and Okwo (2019) state that lack of start-up capital impedes the course of skill acquisition and apprentices do not ultimately acquire sufficient entrepreneurial skills and knowledge for the entrepreneurial development.

Business Skills has a direct and positive relationship with entrepreneurship development among Igbo traders in Anambra State, Nigeria. In other words, 1% increase in Business Skills will bring about 55.6% growths in the entrepreneurship development among Igbo traders in Anambra State, Nigeria. This result is

in line with the findings of Kekeocha, & Nnabuife, (2024) which showed from their survey that apprenticeship system has positive significant impacts on employees' skill development in informal sector and in particular in printing industry. Also, Nwali, Emeali, Ugwa, & Odo, (2024) in his results revealed that there is low level of education among the majority of the selected small-scale businesses in the Southern region of Nigeria and majority acquired their skills through the apprenticeship.

Test of Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested in the study:

Hypothesis One

Ho₁: Start-up capital has no significant influence on the survival rate among Igbo traders in Anambra State, Nigeria.

From table 9, the t-test value of start-up capital is significant at 0.000 level of significant. We, therefore, reject the null hypothesis and conclude that start-up capital has significant influence on the survival rate among Igbo traders in Anambra State, Nigeria.

Hypothesis Two

Ho₂: Business skills have no significant influence on the survival rate among Igbo traders in Anambra State, Nigeria.

From table 9, the t-test value of business skills is significant at 0.020 level of significant. We, therefore, reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternate by concluding that business skills have significant influence on the survival rate among Igbo traders in Anambra State, Nigeria.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusion

In the final analysis, this study has examined apprenticeship and entrepreneurship development among Igbo traders in Anambra state Nigeria. The study has Specifically determined the extent to which start-up capital has influenced the survival rate of Igbo traders in Anambra State, Nigeria; ascertained the extent to which business skills has influenced survival rate of Igbo traders in Anambra State, Nigeria; The study found that start-up capital, and business skills,

In general, the joint effect of the explanatory variables-independent variables-in the model account for 0.841 or 84.1% of the variations in apprenticeship influencing entrepreneurship development among Igbo traders in Anambra State. This implies that 84.1% of the variations in the entrepreneurship development among Igbo traders in Anambra State are being accounted for or explained by the variations in start-up capital, and business skills, While other independent variables not captured in the model explain just 15.9% of the variations in the entrepreneurship development among Igbo traders in Anambra State.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

- 1) To ensure that start-up capital is dully provided to apprentice, parents and representative of the apprentice should ensure a legally documented agreement between the master and the apprentice.
- 2) Parents and representatives of the apprentice should advise their ward on the need to be patient and diligent to carefully learn the business skills from the master because this is the basis for apprenticeship.

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